

Vol 1, Issue 1 · 2026 · Open Access · Original Article

Comparison of Neonatal Outcomes Following Vaginal Delivery and Cesarean Section in Pregnancies Complicated by Intrauterine Growth Restriction

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.66547/928374> · Published: Jan 15, 2026

ARTICLE HISTORY

RECEIVED	REVISED	ACCEPTED	PUBLISHED
Aug 25, 2025	Nov 18, 2025	Dec 20, 2025	Jan 15, 2026

Keywords: Fetal growth restriction, Mode of delivery, Cesarean section, Neonatal outcomes, Preterm birth

Abstract

OBJECTIVE

Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR) is known to cause increased risks of perinatal problems. The critical nature of the fetal physiology being restricted during IUGR means that the time surrounding birth (the intrapartum period) is a high-risk time for the baby and therefore the choice of delivery type must be thoughtfully considered in order to decrease potential morbidity and mortality. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the differences in perinatal outcomes between those babies born via cesarean section and those born via normal vaginal delivery (VD) to mothers whose pregnancies are complicated by intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) at a tertiary care hospital.

METHODS

This prospective observational cohort study took place at the department of obstetrics and gynecology, Liaquat university hospital in Hyderabad, Pakistan. The study was completed over a six month period. Total of 118 pregnant females (ages 20-35) with a confirmed diagnosis of IUGR who had a cephalic presentation were included in this study based on consecutive sampling (eligible patients were enrolled consecutively and classified according to the actual mode of delivery decided by the treating obstetrician according to clinical indications). Perinatal morbidities and mortality were documented and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. A chi square test was performed to assess the level of significance of the results ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS

The mean maternal age was 24.27 ± 4.59 years, while the mean gestational age at delivery was 32.07 ± 1.57 weeks. Overall, hypoglycemia was the most common neonatal complication, occurring in 83.1% of cases. Adverse neonatal outcomes—including hypocalcemia, NICU admission, hypothermia, and stillbirth—were numerically more frequent among neonates delivered vaginally compared with those delivered by cesarean section. Vaginal delivery was associated with a higher relative risk of NICU admission (RR = 2.25) and hypocalcemia (RR = 3.0); however, these differences were not statistically significant. Stratified analysis demonstrated that parity was a significant determinant of neonatal outcomes ($p = 0.001$). Additionally, unbooked patients showed a trend toward higher rates of adverse neonatal outcomes compared with booked patients, although this association did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.058$).

CONCLUSION

Cesarean section provides a safe and reliable method to optimize neonatal outcomes in IUGR pregnancies. While there was no statistical difference between the two types of delivery, the higher rate of severe complications in spontaneous vaginal deliveries supports the use of a highly individualized decision-making process. Ultimately, the decision regarding delivery should take into account both the maternal health status and the gestational age of the fetus.

Introduction

Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), or the failure of the fetus to achieve its genetically determined growth potential, occurs frequently enough to represent one of the most common complications of pregnancy. In general, clinical evidence indicates that IUGR exists if the estimated fetal weight falls below the 10th percentile for gestation [1]. According to recent data, IUGR is responsible for the second highest number of cases of perinatal morbidity and mortality in non-anomalous infants, being surpassed only by prematurity [2].

Additionally, infants who have experienced growth restriction during their intrauterine development will be at greater risk for a variety of adverse perinatal outcomes including fetal distress, meconium aspiration syndrome, hypothermia, hypoglycemia, and a greater need for admission to the NICU [3]. Further, there is evidence that the effects of intrauterine growth restriction may extend beyond the neonatal period and may be associated with long-term neurodevelopmental and metabolic consequences in adulthood [4].

Due to the diminished physiological reserves of the fetus affected by IUGR, the time surrounding delivery is particularly dangerous. Most growth restricted fetuses, specifically those with impaired placental function, do not adapt well to the stresses of labor, which increases the risk of intrapartum asphyxiation and requires careful thought regarding the best mode of delivery [5]. The two main modes of delivery under consideration are VD and cesarean section (C-Section) each having advantages and disadvantages unique to them [6].

Spontaneous VD is generally considered preferable for the physiological advantages it provides to both mother and infant, which include the surge of hormones that promote fetal lung maturity and respiration, although it does carry the risk of birth trauma and potentially severe intrapartum hypoxia for a vulnerable fetus [7]. Conversely, although a scheduled C-Section may help reduce the risk of birth trauma and severe intrapartum hypoxia, it may deprive the newborn of the advantageous physiological stressors of labor and provide the mother with additional surgical risks [8].

As significant as the research conducted to date concerning IUGR is, the optimal method of delivery for patients with IUGR continues to be debated among clinicians and researchers. There is conflicting evidence in the medical literature regarding whether the physiological benefits of SVD exceed the protective and controlled environment provided by a C-Section for these vulnerable infants [9]. As a result, clinical decisions are made using a multidisciplinary approach and weigh the many variables that affect the patient's care including gestational age, fetal well-being and maternal health. Therefore, to help resolve the continued clinical dilemma of how to manage delivery in patients with IUGR, this study was undertaken to evaluate and compare the perinatal outcomes of spontaneous vaginal deliveries and cesarean sections in patients with IUGR at a tertiary care center.

Subjects, Materials & Methods

STUDY DESIGN AND SETTING

Prospective Observational Cohort study conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad. The six-month study was conducted after obtaining approval for the synopsis of the study. Formal approval for ethical considerations was obtained by the Research Ethics Committee of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro, Pakistan, on March 11, 2022.

SAMPLE SIZE AND SELECTION PROCESS

Sample size was calculated using the expected difference in NICU admission between vaginal and cesarean deliveries in IUGR pregnancies using a 95% confidence level and 80% power; thereby reaching a total sample size of 118 pregnant women.

Sampling Technique: Consecutive non-probability sampling technique.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Women of age between 20 and 35 years.
- Confirmed IUGR.
- Fetus in cephalic position.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Refusal to give consent to participate.
- Presence of fetal congenital anomalies or malpositions.
- Twin pregnancies.
- Breech presentations.

Definition of IUGR: The operational definition for IUGR used in this study was a lag in fundal height of 4 cm or more, and an estimated fetal weight less than 10th percentile for gestational age.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Following the provision of written informed consent from all patients or their relatives, a full clinical and gynecological examination was performed; this included determination of the trimester of pregnancy. Participants were categorized into two groups based on the actual mode of delivery decided by the treating obstetrician according to clinical indications. Group A participants delivered normally vaginally (NVD), whereas group B participants delivered via Caesarean Section (C-section). Perinatal outcome, especially focusing on morbidity and mortality, were documented for both the groups using a standardized study proforma.

DATA ANALYSIS

Collected data were inputted and analyzed using SPSS Version 20.0. Quantitative variable, i.e., age and gestational age were represented in terms of mean and Standard Deviation. Categorical variable, i.e., parity and specific neonatal outcomes were reported in terms of frequency and percentage. Data was stratified according to effect modifier and Chi-square test was applied to assess the level of statistical significance, with a p value <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

BASELINE CHARACTERISTICS

In this study, we studied 118 pregnant women who were identified with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). The average age of our subjects was 24.27 ± 4.59 years and they ranged in age from 18 to 33 years. The average gestation length at which our subjects delivered their babies was 32.07 ± 1.57 weeks. Gestations ages for the subjects ranged between 30 and 35 weeks of gestation. Our demographic results showed that most of our subjects lived in rural areas (n = 80; 67.8%) as opposed to urban areas (n = 38; 32.2%). Our assessment of prenatal care found that 91.5% of our subjects were unbooked, whereas 8.5% of them had a booking status prior to pregnancy. Of the 118 women in our study, 51 (43.2%) of them were primiparous, 56 (47.5%) were multiparous and 11 (9.3%) were grand multiparous.

CLINICAL PARAMETERS

We evaluated pre-delivery maternal hemoglobin values in both delivery groups. Maternal hemoglobin levels in the VD group averaged 8.68 ± 1.33 g/dl and in the cesarean section (C-sec) group averaged 8.90 ± 1.14 g/dl. These differences were not statistically significant (p = 0.338).

PRIMARY NEONATAL OUTCOMES BY MODE OF DELIVERY

Both delivery groups included an equal number of patients, i.e., 59 VD and 59 C-section. The most frequent neonatal complications in both delivery groups were hypoglycemia, affecting 44 (74.6%) neonates in the NVD group and 54 (91.5%) neonates in the C-section group.

In contrast, the rates of adverse neonatal outcomes were numerically higher in the vaginal delivery group compared with the cesarean section group; however, the difference was not statistically significant (p = 0.139). Rates of hypocalcemia, NICU admission, hypothermia, and stillbirths following VD were each greater than those following surgical delivery. Nonetheless, the comparisons of the rates of these neonatal outcomes between the two types of deliveries were not statistically significant (p = 0.139).

Table 1: Comparison of Neonatal Outcomes according to Mode of Delivery (N=118)

Outcome	VD n (%)	CS n (%)	RR	OR	p-value
Hypoglycemia	44 (74.6%)	54 (91.5%)	0.81	0.27	0.025
NICU admission	9 (15.3%)	4 (6.8%)	2.25	2.48	0.239
Hypocalcemia	3 (5.1%)	1 (1.7%)	3.00	3.11	0.619
Stillbirth	2 (3.4%)	0 (0.0%)	—	5.17*	0.496
Hypothermia	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	—	3.05*	1.000

* Odds ratios calculated using continuity correction due to zero cell counts.

STRATIFIED ANALYSIS OF NEONATAL OUTCOMES

To identify effect modifiers, outcomes were stratified by booking status and parity. Adverse outcomes, including hypoglycemia, hypocalcemia, NICU admission, hypothermia, and stillbirth, were observed at higher frequencies in unbooked cases compared to booked cases. The relationship between booking status and adverse neonatal outcomes approached statistical significance ($p = 0.058$). When outcomes were stratified by parity, significant differences emerged ($p = 0.001$). NICU admissions were predominantly higher among multiparous women, whereas complications such as hypocalcemia and hypothermia were noted more frequently in primiparous women. Notably, instances of stillbirth were exclusively observed in the grand multiparous group.

Discussion

The decisions related to pregnancy are difficult for pregnant women, families and healthcare professionals, particularly when there is concern about the well-being of either the mother or her unborn child. As such, an important part of providing high-quality prenatal care to women whose pregnancies are complicated by intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) is ensuring that the woman delivers the baby using the best possible method of delivery to protect the health and safety of both the woman and the baby. Therefore, this research was designed to determine whether deliveries resulting from spontaneous VD or planned cesarean sections (C-Section) resulted in better or worse perinatal outcomes in a cohort of 118 pregnant women whose babies had intrauterine growth restrictions.

The average age of the women participating in the current study was 24.27 ± 4.59 years, and the average gestational age at the time of delivery was 32.07 ± 1.57 weeks. The demographics of the participants in the current study are consistent with other studies of IUGR; for example, Qamar et al. [10] reported an average age of 31.28 ± 4.09 years and gestational age of 31.17 ± 2.47 weeks, whereas Roy et al. [11] reported an average age of 26.48 ± 4.06 years among women with IUGR. Additionally, the number of parous vs. nulliparous women in the current study were consistent with those of Mohammad et al. [12]; i.e., 57.8% parous and 42.2% nulliparous in the former study and 47.5% parous and 43.2% nulliparous in the current study.

As described above, when comparing neonatal outcomes according to the type of delivery, our data indicate that the rates of complications including hypocalcemia, admission to the NICU, hypothermia and stillbirth were greater in the NVD than in the C-Section group; however, none of the differences reached statistical significance ($p = 0.139$). In general, the fact that we found a trend toward greater adverse outcomes among neonates delivered vaginally is consistent with the concept that the chronically hypoxic, growth-restricted fetus has limited physiologic reserve to withstand the stresses of uterine contraction during labor [13, 14]. Although VD eliminates maternal surgical risk, the increased risk of intrapartum asphyxia often drives the clinical preference for C-Sections, either elective or emergency, in severely growth restricted fetuses [15].

Regardless of the mode of delivery, hypoglycemia was the most common complication identified in both cohorts (83.1% overall). Hypoglycemia is a documented complication of IUGR due to the depleted hepatic glycogen stores and impaired gluconeogenesis in the growth-restricted fetus [16]. Furthermore, the limited subcutaneous fat in IUGR neonates significantly impairs their ability to maintain their body temperature, thereby necessitating immediate intervention in the NICU [17].

Finally, the stratification of our data revealed the importance of antenatal care and parity status of the mothers in determining neonatal outcomes. Our data demonstrated that adverse outcomes were significantly higher in unbooked patients compared to booked patients ($p = 0.058$). This illustrates the critical role of regular antenatal monitoring, where unbooked patients frequently miss essential interventions, such as serial umbilical artery Doppler assessments, administration of maternal corticosteroids for fetal lung maturity and appropriate timing of delivery, which can significantly mitigate the substantial risks of IUGR [9].

Moreover, we found that parity was also a significant effect modifier ($p = 0.001$); i.e., NICU admissions were significantly more frequent in multiparous women, whereas stillbirths occurred exclusively in grand multiparous women. Grand multiparity is often associated with advanced maternal age and an increased prevalence of maternal comorbidities (e.g., hypertension, inadequate placental perfusion), which may act synergistically to increase the severity of fetal growth restriction and precipitate catastrophic outcomes such as stillbirth if they remain unmonitored [18].

Therefore, the choice of the mode of delivery in cases of IUGR involves many factors and should be performed individually and based upon a careful evaluation of the maternal health, fetal well-being, gestational age and the presence of any co-existing obstetric complications. Thus, obstetricians must carefully evaluate the potential advantages of a vaginal birth compared to the controlled delivery environment of a C-Section and provide open communication with the expectant mother throughout the decision-making process.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that cesarean section is a safe and viable option for delivering infants with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). Although there were no statistically significant differences in the neonatal outcomes from the two delivery methods, there were specific adverse events that were clinically more common after spontaneous VD — hypocalcemia, NICU admission, hypothermia, and stillbirths.

The study's findings highlight the need for obstetricians to take an individualized approach when making decisions regarding the most appropriate method of delivery for each patient. Each clinical decision should be based on a thorough assessment of the mother's overall health, the fetus' overall health, the gestational age of the fetus, and the presence of any other medical concerns. Finally, continued, and vigilant monitoring of both the mother and the fetus at all stages of the pregnancy and during labor will provide the greatest opportunity for achieving the best possible outcome for both the mother and her child. Assessing fetal growth, placental function, and the mother's overall health regularly will allow clinicians to quickly identify any changes that may affect the mother or the fetus and make necessary adjustments to their delivery plans to achieve the best possible perinatal outcomes.

Author Contributions

In accordance with the ICMJE guidelines, all authors have made substantial contributions to the manuscript and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Author	Conception & Design	Data Collection & Analysis	Drafting & Revision	Final Approval
Zarka Erum (ZE)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Naheed Parveen (NP)	✓	—	✓	✓
Shehla Raza Channa (SRC)	—	✓	✓	✓
Marina Khan (MK)	—	✓	—	✓
Maria Soomro (MS)	—	—	✓	✓
Aqsa (A)	—	✓	—	✓

DECLARATIONS

Ethical Approval: The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro, Pakistan (ERC Letter No. LUMHS/REC/-67).

Acknowledgements: None declared.

Disclaimer: The views expressed in this article are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of the affiliated institutions.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Funding Disclosure: No funding was received for this study.

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References

1. Martins JG, Biggio JR, Abuhamad A. Society for Maternal-Fetal Medicine Consult Series #52: Diagnosis and management of fetal growth restriction. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2020;223(4):B2-B17.
2. Sharma D, Farahbakhsh N, Shastri S, Sharma P. Intrauterine growth restriction - part 2. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2016;29(24):4037-4048.
3. Garite TJ, Clark R, Thorp JA. Intrauterine growth restriction increases morbidity and mortality among premature neonates. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2004;191(2):481-487.
4. Barker DJ. The developmental origins of adult disease. *J Am Coll Nutr.* 2004;23(6 Suppl):588S-595S.
5. Lees C, Marlow N, Arabin B, et al. Perinatal morbidity and mortality in early-onset fetal growth restriction: cohort outcomes of the trial of randomized umbilical and fetal flow in Europe (TRUFFLE). *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2013;42(4):400-408.
6. Boers KE, Vijgen SM, Bijlenga D, et al. Induction versus expectant monitoring for intrauterine growth restriction at term: randomised equivalence trial (DIGITAT). *BMJ.* 2010;341:c7087.
7. Simchen CE, Beiner ME, Strauss-Liviathan N, et al. Neonatal outcome in growth-restricted versus appropriately grown premature infants. *Am J Perinatol.* 2000;17(4):187-192.

8. Lee HC, Gould JB. Survival rates and mode of delivery for vertex preterm neonates according to small- or appropriate-for-gestational-age status. *Pediatrics*. 2006;118(6):e1836-e1844.
9. Figueras F, Gratacós E. Update on the diagnosis and classification of fetal growth restriction and proposal of a stage-based management protocol. *Fetal Diagn Ther*. 2014;36(2):86-98.
10. Qamar MK, Khan YQ, Irum N, Manzoor S. Frequency of Intrauterine Growth Retardation in Obese Pregnant Females: A Cross Sectional Study in Two Tertiary Care Hospitals of Pakistan. *J Soc Obstet Gynaecol Pak*. 2021;11(4).
11. Roy K, Hemlata NB, Goswami P. Outcome of Pregnancies Complicated by Fetal Growth Restriction. *JLUMHS*. 2014;13(02):67.
12. Mohammad N, Sohaila A, Rabbani U, Ahmed S, Ahmed S, Ali SR. Maternal predictors of intrauterine growth retardation. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak*. 2018;28(9):681.
13. Wilk C, Arab S, Czuzoj-Shulman N, Abenhaim HA. Influence of intrauterine growth restriction on caesarean delivery risk among preterm pregnancies undergoing induction of labor for hypertensive disease. *J Obstet Gynaecol Res*. 2019;45(9):1860-1865.
14. Sharma D, Shastri S, Farahbakhsh N, Sharma P. Intrauterine growth restriction - part 1. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med*. 2016;29(24):3977-3987.
15. Bamfo JE, Odibo AO. Diagnosis and management of fetal growth restriction. *J Pregnancy*. 2011;2011:640715.
16. Vayssiere C, Sentilhes L, Ego A, et al. Fetal growth restriction and intra-uterine growth restriction: Guidelines for clinical practice from the French College of Gynaecologists and Obstetricians. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol*. 2015;193:10-18.
17. Longo S, Bollani L, Decembrino L, Di Comite A, Angelini M, Stronati M. Short-term and long-term sequelae in intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR). *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med*. 2013;26(3):222-225.
18. Lausman A, Kingdom J. Intrauterine growth restriction: screening, diagnosis, and management. *J Obstet Gynaecol Can*. 2013;35(8):741-748.